

EFFECT OF RESISTANCE TRAINING ON PHYSICAL FITNESS COMPONENT AMONG BASKETBALL PLAYERS AT SCHOOL LEVEL

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of resistance training on physical fitness component among school basketball players. To achieve the purpose of the present study, thirty school basketball players from Chennai, Tamilnadu were selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 15 to 17 years. The subjects were divided into two equal groups at random. The subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen subjects each. Group I acted as Experimental Group (Resistance Training) and Group II acted as Control Group. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. The duration of experimental period was 6 weeks. After the experimental treatment, all the thirty subjects were tested on their physical fitness component. This final test scores formed as post test scores of the subjects. The pre test and post test scores were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to find out the significance among the mean differences. In all cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed to test hypotheses. It was observed that the six weeks of experimental group have significantly improved speed of school basketball players

Key Words: Resistance Training, Speed, Basketball Players.

Introduction:

Resistance training is a form of strength training in which each effort is performed against a specific opposing force generated by resistance. Resistance exercise is used to develop the strength and size of skeletal muscles. Properly performed resistance training can provide significant functional benefits and improvement in overall health and well being. Resistance training as an exercise programme in which free or stationary weights are used for the purpose of increasing muscular strength, muscular endurance, power and body composition through which skills can be improved (Kartikeyan, 2014).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of resistance training on physical fitness component among school basketball players. To achieve the purpose of the present study, thirty school basketball players from Chennai, Tamilnadu were selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 15 to 17 years. The subjects were divided into two equal groups at random. The subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen subjects each. Group I acted as Experimental Group (Resistance Training) and Group II acted as Control Group. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. The duration of experimental period was 6 weeks. After the experimental treatment, all the thirty subjects were tested on their physical fitness component. This final test scores formed as post test scores of the subjects. The pre test and post test scores were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to find out the significance among the mean differences. In all cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed to test hypotheses.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Speed of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	7.47	7.45	BG	0.003	1	0.003	0.70
			WG	0.12	28	0.005	
Post Test Mean	6.80	7.44	BG	3.05	1	3.05	555.54*
			WG	0.15	28	0.005	
Adjusted Post Mean	6.80	7.44	BG	2.99	1	2.99	527.57*
			WG	0.15	27	0.006	

* Significant at 0.05 level Table value for df 1 and 28 was 4.20, 1 and 27 was 4.21

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of speed of experimental and control groups were 6.80 and 7.44 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 527.57 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the

study indicates that there was a significant difference among experimental and control groups on speed. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups differ significantly. The pre, post and adjusted post mean values of speed of both experimental and control groups are graphically represented in the figure-I.

Figure 1: Shows the Mean Values on Speed of Experimental Group and Control Groups

Conclusion:

It was observed that the six weeks of experimental group have significantly improved speed of school basketball players.

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